

Data Steward's RDM Elements List

General	
Research Group/Unit	
Number of PIs/Professors	
Number of PhDs/Postdoc	
Number of Dedicated RDM Personnel	

Research Data Management			
Metadata standards			
Data repositories			
Documentation			
File Organization	Data Centrally stored <input type="checkbox"/>	Only clean contents <input type="checkbox"/>	Readme about agreed file structure <input type="checkbox"/>
	Project centred hierarchy <input type="checkbox"/>	Tag based file name <input type="checkbox"/>	
Research Workflows/Procedures			
Research Data Types/Formats			
Tools/Instruments			
Software/Scripts			
Version Management	Tools:		
	Coding standards Used <input type="checkbox"/>	Code Comments Provided <input type="checkbox"/>	Readme files Provided <input type="checkbox"/>
Data storage			

Data Security	
Data Sharing	
Data De-identification (Anonymization, Pseudonymization)	
Data Archiving Policy/Workflows	
Researcher Offboarding Protocol/Checklist	